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In vitro osteogenesis of hMSCs on collagen membranes embedded within LEGO[®]-inspired 3D printed PCL constructs for mandibular bone repair

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Abstract

The field of bone tissue engineering aims to develop an effective and aesthetical bone graft substitute capable of repairing large mandibular defects. However, graft failure resulting from necrosis and insufficient integration with native tissue due to lack of oxygen and nutrient transportation remains a concern. To overcome these drawbacks, this study aims to develop a 3D printed polycaprolactone layered construct with a LEGO[®]-inspired interlocking mechanism enabling spatial distribution of biological components. To highlight its *in vitro* osteogenic potential, human mesenchymal stromal cells are cultured onto Bio-Gide[®] Compressed collagen (Col) membranes, which are embedded within the layered construct for 28 d. The osteogenic response is assessed through the measurement of proliferation, relevant markers for osteogenesis including alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity, expression of transcriptional genes (SP7, RUNX2/SOX9) as well matrix-related genes (COL1A1, ALPL, IBSP, SPP1), osteoprotegerin secretion. *In vitro* osteogenic differentiation results showed increased levels of these osteogenic markers, indicating the layered construct's potential to support osteogenesis. In this study, a novel workflow of 3D printing a patient-specific LEGO[®]-inspired layered construct that can spatially deliver biological elements was successfully demonstrated. These layered constructs have the potential to be employed as a bone tissue engineering strategy, with particular focus on the repair of large mandibular defects.

1. Introduction

The treatment of large mandibular bone defects resulting from trauma, tumor removal, congenital deformities, osteoradionecrosis, or infections requires intricate surgical procedures involving autologous bone grafting [1, 2]. However, this is associated with major drawbacks including donor side morbidities, prolonged operation time, limited availability, and inability to form patient-specific geometries [3, 4]. Alternative approaches such as using recombinant human bone morphogenetic protein-2 (rhBMP-2) delivered through a collagen (Col) sponge are not

exempt from their own drawbacks. The side effects of rhBMP-2 include postoperative inflammation, ectopic bone formation, osteoclast-mediated bone resorption, inappropriate adipogenesis, and elevated risk of cancer [5].

To address these concerns, bone tissue engineering emerged as a focal point of research, aiming to develop a bone graft substitute that can overcome these limitations, while achieving both functional and aesthetical outcomes [6]. However, one of the primary causes of construct failure are the formation of necrotic cores and inadequate integration with native tissue due to lack of oxygen

and nutrient transportation, often resulting in non-unions [7]. A solution to this issue is to divide the scaffold into layers, therefore allowing spatial integration of biological elements within the scaffold's core (figure 1). A layered approach creates possibilities for constructs with multiple porosities, cell types, membranes, materials, co-culture systems, or using multiple of the listed options in a multicomponent system. To achieve the creation of a layered construct the implementation of an interlocking system is a promising approach, inspired by the concept of the LEGO® bricks. In between the multiple layers, biological elements can be embedded aiding in ignition of the osteogenic process and attraction of vessels from the surrounding native environment to achieve guided bone regeneration.

3D printing polycaprolactone (PCL) offers an easy and precise fabrication mechanism, mechanical strength, and biodegradability [8], all favorable properties to create a bone graft substitute suitable for repairing load-bearing mandibular defects. However, PCL's intrinsic lack of biological cues makes it an inadequate candidate to deliver biological agents [9]. Col membranes emerge as the ideal transporter to convey biological substances such as regenerative progenitor cells or biological factors. They provide molecular cues for cell migration and promotion of osteogenesis [10–12]. Furthermore, they have a thin structure, which makes them well-suited to be easily placed within a layered construct, where they can assist in keeping the implanted cells within each layer.

In this study, the aim was to establish a workflow for creating patient-specific 3D printed LEGO®-inspired layered construct featuring an interlocking system capable of accommodating Col membranes (CLIP-Col). Clinically available Col membranes of Bio-Gide® were selected due to its established use in clinical practice and capacity for guiding bone regeneration [13, 14]. Bio-Gide® Col membranes have previously been shown to allow cell migration due to its open meshwork with porous structure [15]. To demonstrate the CLIP-Col osteogenic potential, *in vitro* osteogenic differentiation of human mesenchymal stromal cells (hMSCs) seeded onto Col membranes embedded within the LEGO®-inspired layered construct was performed.

2. Materials and methods

All reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich unless otherwise stated.

2.1. Design and 3D printing of a patient-specific LEGO®-inspired layered construct

To demonstrate the creation of a patient-specific layered construct inspired by the LEGO® brick system a workflow was developed. A SYNBONE® mandibular defect with random shape was created and scanned using micro-computed tomography (μ CT) (vivaCT

40). The object based on the geometries of the defect was rendered using the Amira image processing software and exported as STL file. The object file was then virtually sliced into 4 layered parts with LEGO®-inspired bricks and holes within the individual parts using the Autodesk Fusion 360 software. The STL files of the 4 layered parts were converted into g-code using the MM Converter software (RegenHu) and 3D printed using a 3D Discovery® bioprinter (RegenHU). PCL pellets (average MW: 45 000 g mol⁻¹) were placed into the heated reservoir chamber of the 3D printer, where they were melted at 75 °C. The PCL was pressed to the extruding chamber with a temperature of 70 °C through a rotor system set at 21 revs min⁻¹. Equipped with a 0.33 mm stainless steel needle the PCL was extruded onto a glass slide heated to 37 °C using a heating table to 3D print the 4 individual layered parts with an infill density of 40%. Upon 3D printing the 4 parts can be clipped together to form a patient-specific layered construct.

2.2. Design and 3D printing of two-part layered PCL construct for *in vitro* osteogenic assessment

The 3D printed layered construct used for the osteogenic experiment was composed of two parts, top (with LEGO®-inspired holes) and bottom (with LEGO®-inspired bricks), with an interlocking mechanism with a tight fit upon clipping. The construct has a round shape with a diameter of 15.3 mm to fit into a 24-tissue culture well plate to demonstrate the *in vitro* osteogenesis of hMSCs cultured on Col membranes embedded within the layered construct. The bottom part has a height of 1 mm without the bricks and the top part has a height of 1.8 mm. The two bricks on the bottom part of the construct (1 × 5 × 1.3 mm) were placed 1.8 mm apart from the edge and 9.8 mm apart from each other leaving space for the Col membrane. The holes of the top part (1.2 × 5.2 × 1.3 mm) are precisely placed over the position of the bricks as the counterpart. The Col membrane can be placed in between the interlocking two parts. The two components of the layered construct are printed as described in section 2.1 with differences being the use of the PCL (average MW: 36 000–45 000 g mol⁻¹, iChemical), the reservoir chamber set at 125 °C, the extruding chamber set at 120 °C and the infill density set to 40% to obtain a macro-porous construct. Subsequently, layered parts were sterilized using a cold ethylene oxide gas protocol, degassed under vacuum, before being used for the osteogenic experiments.

2.3. Mechanical testing LEGO®-inspired layered construct

Mechanical compression tests of 3D printed LEGO®-inspired scaffolds ($n = 6$) were performed using LTM 1 (ZwickRoell). Compression test was performed using a pre-load of 0.25 N, speed of 0.1%/s. Compressive modulus was calculated from the slope

from the linear region of the stress–strain curve between 5%–10% strain.

2.4. Cell isolation and culture of hMSCs

Human bone marrow aspirates were obtained with informed consent of all donors. Isolation, cryopreservation, and culture expansion of hMSCs were conducted following published protocols [16, 17]. In short, cells were expanded in T300 flasks (cell density 3×10^3 cells cm^{-2}) and cultured under standard cell culture conditions of 37 °C with 5% CO_2 and 90% humidity with 3 media changes per week. The expansion medium consisted of α -MEM (Gibco) supplemented with 10% (v/v) fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Corning), 100 U ml^{-1} Penicillin, 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ Streptomycin (PEN/STREP) (Gibco), and 5 ng ml^{-1} basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF, Fitzgerald Industries International). hMSCs from 4 female donors between the age of 48 and 71 years all at passage 3 were used.

2.5. Osteogenic differentiation of hMSCs

hMSCs were harvested using 0.05% Trypsin-EDTA and seeded at a density of 15×10^3 cells cm^{-2} in duplicates onto either cell-culture plastic (CCP) coverslips (SARSTEDT AG) or Bio-Gide® Compressed bilayer Col membranes (Geistlich) based on porcine Col type I and III embedded within the 3D printed layered PCL constructs (figure 2). Cell-laden constructs were placed within a Costar® 24-well Clear Flat Bottom Ultra-Low Attachment Multiple Well Plates (Corning) and secured using a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) (SYLGARD™184 Silicone Elastomer, Dow) ring, which was press-fitted into each well to prevent floating of the whole PCL/Col construct. For

the first 24 h, cells were cultured in basal medium, which consisted of low glucose (1 g l^{-1})–DMEM (LG-DMEM) (Gibco) supplemented with 10% (v/v) FBS and 100 U ml^{-1} PEN/STREP. Subsequently, the media was either maintained with basal medium or switched to osteogenic medium, which consisted of basal medium supplemented with 10 nM dexamethasone (Dexa), 5 mM β -glycerophosphate (BGP) and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ L-ascorbic acid-2-phosphate (AA2P). In summary, the experiment is performed under 4 different conditions: 1) CCP basal medium; 2) CCP osteogenic medium; 3) CLIP + Col basal medium and 4) CLIP + Col osteogenic medium for 28 d under standard culture conditions.

2.6. Quantification of ALP activity and DNA content

At day 0, 7, 14 and 28, ALP activity and DNA content were measured as previously described [17]. In short, Col membranes were taken out of the layered construct and cells were lysed with 0.1% Triton X-100 in 10 mM TrisHCl. Subsequently, the enzymatic reaction was started by adding alkaline buffer solution, substrate solution (25 mg ml^{-1} phosphate substrate in 1 mM diethanolamine) and Milli-Q water and stopped by adding 0.1 M NaOH solution after 15 min of incubation at 37 °C. The absorbance was read at 405 nm using the Infinite® 200 PRO plate reader (Tecan). ALP activity was normalized to the DNA content. DNA concentration was quantified at day 0, 7, 14 and 28 using the CyQuant™ Cell Proliferation Assay (Invitrogen) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Cell lysate was transferred into a 96 clear bottom well plate, working solution containing dye was added, incubated for 5 min and fluorescence was

Table 1. Primer and probe (forward, reverse and probe sequence) and TaqMan gene expression assays (applied biosystem assay ID) for gene expression analysis. Probes for RPLP0, RUNX2, and COL1A1 were modified with FAM at 5' and TAMRA at 3'. Probes in Taqman gene expression assays were conjugated with FAM at 5' and NFQ-MGB at 3'.

	Gene	Forward primer sequence	Reverse primer sequence	Probe sequence	Assay ID
Primer and probe	RPLP0	5'-TGG GCA AGA ACA CCA TGA TG-3'	5'-CGG ATA TGA GGC AGC AGT TTC-3'	5'-AGG GCA CCT GGA AAA CAA CCC AGC-3'	—
	RUNX2	5'-AGC AAG GTT CAA CGA TCT GAG AT-3'	5'-TTT GTG AAG ACG GTT ATG GTC AA-3'	5'-TGA AAC TCT TGC CTC GTC CAC TCC G-3'	—
	COL1A1	5'-CCC TGG AAA GAA TGG AGA TGA T-3'	5'-ACT GAA ACC TCT GTG TCC CTT CA-3'	5'-CGG GCA ATC CTC GAG CAC CCT -3'	—
TaqMan Gene Expression Assays	SOX9	—	—	—	Hs00165814_m1
	ALPL	—	—	—	Hs00758162_m1
	IBSP	—	—	—	Hs00173720_m1
	SP7	—	—	—	Hs00541729_m1
	SPP1	—	—	—	Hs00959010_m1

read at 490/530 nm using Infinite[®] 200 PRO plate reader. The DNA content was normalized to the corresponding surface area.

2.7. ALP staining

On day 14, CLIP-Col constructs were stained for ALP using the alkaline phosphatase staining kit (Procedure No. 85) according to the company's instructions. In short, cells were washed 3x with phosphate buffered saline (PBS), fixed with 4% neutral buffered formalin for 30 min and, after 3x Milli-Q water rinses, then stained with the alkaline dye solution for 30 min at room temperature. 50 ml alkaline dye solution was composed of one Fast Blue RR Salt capsule and 2 ml Naphthol AS-MX Phosphate Alkaline solution. Upon Milli-Q water rinsing the samples were imaged.

2.8. Quantification of OPG production

The secretion of OPG by hMSCs cultured on constructs was determined via ELISA (R&D) according to the manufacturer's protocol, measured in

the conditioned medium that was collected at every medium change over 28 d of osteogenic differentiation and pooled together per week.

2.9. RNA isolation and reverse transcription-quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR)

Cells were harvested for gene expression analysis on day 0, 7, 14 and 28. Col membranes were taken out of the CLIP-Col constructs and RNA isolation and RT-qPCR was performed using the QuantStudio[™] Flex Real-Time PCR System as previously described [17]. Reverse transcription was performed using the Superscript Vilo cDNA Synthesis Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to the company's instructions. RUNX2, COL1A1, SOX9, ALPL, IBSP, SP7 and SPP1 gene expressions were investigated (table 1). The $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ method was applied for data analysis using RPLP0 as an endogenous normalizer and the monolayer before cell seeding on CCP or CLIP-Col structures as a calibrator.

Figure 3. Schematic on workflow and design of patient-specific LEGO®-inspired bone graft substitute and simplified construct for proof-of-concept *in vitro* osteogenesis. (a) Workflow of creating patient-specific layered construct inspired by LEGO®: 1. Images of a SYNBONE® mandibular empty defect scanned using μ CT, 2. using μ CT images a STL. File is created and sliced into individual LEGO®-inspired layers, 3. LEGO®-inspired layers are 3D printed using PCL, 4. LEGO®-inspired layers are clipped together to form the complete construct to match the defect site, and 5. Implantation of the patient-specific construct into the mandibular defect. (b) Virtual schematic, STL format including dimensions, of the design used for *in vitro* osteogenic differentiation experiments. (c) Images of the assembled and separate top and bottom layer of the 3D printed PCL LEGO®-inspired construct with embedded Col membrane using for *in vitro* osteogenic differentiation experiments. (d) Stress-strain curve LEGO®-inspired construct, $n = 6$. (e) Compressive modulus LEGO®-inspired construct between 5%–10% strain, $n = 6$. Created with BioRender.com.

2.10. Statistical analysis

Results are expressed as mean + standard deviation, unless otherwise stated. Analysis of the difference between groups was performed by two-way ANOVA (for two or more timepoints). Results were obtained from experiments that were repeated at least 3 or 4 times, using different donors each time. All statistical analysis were performed using GraphPad Prism 8 (GraphPad Software Inc., USA). Asterisks denote statistical significance as follows: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$, and *ns* = no significance.

3. Results

3.1. Design and workflow of patient-specific 3D printed LEGO®-inspired layered construct for mandibular defect repair

The design of the LEGO®-inspired layered construct (figure 3(b)) was established after considering multiple design options for an interlocking construct. Approaches such as rotational interlocking or construct that could slide into each other were explored, however the LEGO®-inspired construct was selected due to its easy 3D fabrication and available space for

the placement of a Col membrane. The dimensions of the bricks in the bottom layer allow for precise and easy fabrication, as well as for robust interconnection between the bottom and top layer. Furthermore, the size of the bricks was kept to a minimal to keep the internal structure as porous as possible without losing stability of the interlocking system. The porosity of the bottom and top layer of the construct mimics was chosen big enough to allow for vessel infiltration [18, 19]. Additionally, the porosity allows for the diffusion of nutrients and oxygen.

To demonstrate workflow and clinical compatibility, a mandibular defect was created in a SYNBONE® model (figure 3(a)). This defect was then scanned using μ CT imaging and an STL file for a patient-specific scaffold was generated. The PCL scaffold was printed as 4 individual layers with each possessing the LEGO®-inspired holes on the top layer, and the bottom layer containing the interlocking bricks to clip the layers together into the defect filling construct. The LEGO®-inspired bricks and holes of the layers had a tight fit to maintain the structure of the construct. The macro-porous 3D printed layered construct shows precise defect fitting upon implantation in the defect site, a highly desired characteristic for patient's aesthetics. Further, the layered construct allows for the delivery and long-term *in vitro* osteogenic culture of hMSCs-laden Col membranes, which was demonstrated by 3D printing a round two-part layered construct that fits a 24 well cell culture plate (figures 3(b) and (c)). Compressive mechanical testing revealed a compressive modulus of the LEGO®-inspired construct of 1200 kPa (figures 3(d) and (e)).

3.2. Osteogenic differentiation of hMSCs on CLIP-Col

The ALP activity (figure 4(a)), DNA content (figure 4(b)) and ALP activity normalized to DNA content (figure 4(c)), show a trend of mean upregulation of osteogenically driven cells cultured on CLIP-Col compared to cells cultured under basal medium conditions over 28 d and normalized ALP activity shows similar responses to cells cultured on CCP.

ALP staining confirms the increased protein expression of osteogenically treated cells on CCP and CLIP-Col with increased stained area at day 14 shown by two representative donors (figure 4(d)). Notably, the PCL macroporous printed scaffold also displayed ALP positivity, demonstrating that MSCs are able to migrate off the collagen membrane and populate the scaffold itself.

OPG secretion in conditioned medium shows increased concentrations in cells cultured on CLIP-Col and CCP under osteogenic medium conditions compared to basal medium (figure 4(e)). Similar OPG concentrations were found for cells cultured on CLIP-Col and CCP.

Two-way ANOVA was used to analyze the data, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, and **** $p < 0.0001$.

CCP = Cell-culture plastic, Col = Collagen, CLIP-Col = Col membranes embedded in 3D printed LEGO®-inspired PCL constructs, ALP = Alkaline phosphatase, OPG = Osteoprotegerin.

Gene expression of transcriptional genes (RUNX2, SOX9, SP7) as well as matrix-related genes (COL1A1, ALPL, IBSP, SPP1) were measured (figure 5).

The ratio of transcription factor expression between RUNX2 and SOX9, an indicator for osteogenesis [20], shows an upregulation of cells upon osteogenic treatment at day 7 and 14 and a downregulation at day 28 compared to basal conditions (figures 5(a)–(c)). SP7, the osterix encoding gene, is an important osteogenic transcription factor [21]. The SP7 fold change gene expression trend of osteogenically driven cells is upregulated at day 14 for cells on CLIP-Col and at day 7 and 14 for CCP compared to basal medium conditions (figure 5(d)). The gene expression of transcription factors is important for hMSCs trilineage differentiation and reveals an overall upregulation for osteogenic markers (SP7 and RUNX2/SOX9) upon osteogenic medium treatment.

COL1A1, alpha-1 type 1 Col encoding gene, is an important early osteogenic marker for matrix production of osteogenically differentiated hMSCs. The fold change trend of COL1A1 expression is upregulated in the basal and osteogenic groups (figure 5(e)). The trend of osteogenically driven cells on CLIP-Col is slightly upregulated at day 7, increased at day 14 and slightly downregulated at day 28 compared to the cells cultured under basal condition. ALPL, the ALP encoding gene, is an intermediate osteogenic marker and responsible for cleaving phosphates, important for the mineralization of the extracellular matrix. Cells cultured under osteogenic medium conditions show a similar trend of ALPL at day 7, followed by a strong upregulation at day 14 and 28, compared to cells cultured under basal medium (figure 5(f)). IBSP, bone sialoprotein encoding gene, is a late-stage osteoblast differentiation marker for matrix production of osteogenically differentiated hMSCs. The fold change of IBSP expression, is downregulated at day 7 and then upregulated at day 14 and 28 of cells on CLIP-Col in the osteogenic medium groups, while for the basal medium at day 7 it is slightly upregulated followed by day 14 being slightly downregulated and upregulated at day 28 (figure 5(g)). SPP1, osteopontin encoding gene, is a late-stage osteogenic marker for matrix production. The SPP1 fold change expression is upregulated for all groups, with a slightly higher upregulation in the osteogenic group of cells on CLIP-Col compared to the basal medium at day 14 and 28 (figure 5(h)). The gene expression of important matrix-related osteogenic markers [22] is upregulated in the early (COL1A1), intermediate (ALPL), and the

Figure 4. Osteogenic differentiation of hMSCs on CCP or CLIP-Col. (a) ALP activity after 0, 7, 14 and 28 d, $n = 4$. (b) Quantification of DNA content after 0, 7, 14 and 28 d, $n = 4$. (c) ALP activity normalized to DNA content after 0, 7, 14 and 28 d, $n = 4$. (d) Representative images of two donors of ALP staining (blue) after 14 d, scalebar = 5 mm, $n = 4$. (e) OPG secretion in culture medium pooled together per week, $n = 3$.

late-stage osteogenic differentiation (IBSP and SPP1) of hMSCs cultured in osteogenic medium on CLIP-Col.

Two-way ANOVA was used to analyze the data, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$, and $****p < 0.0001$.

CCP = Cell-culture plastic, Col = Collagen, CLIP-Col = Col membranes embedded in 3D printed LEGO[®]-inspired PCL constructs.

4. Discussion

In this study, the objective was to develop a patient-specific 3D printed PCL layered construct clipped

together using an interlocking mechanism inspired by LEGO[®] bricks. Here, a systematic workflow for generating patient-specific 3D printed layered constructs with the potential to deliver biological elements for a mandibular defect repair was successfully established.

Furthermore, the aim was to demonstrate proof-of-concept of this LEGO[®]-inspired layered construct combined with commercially available Bio-Gide[®] Col membranes, commonly used in clinical settings, (CLIP-Col) by *in vitro* osteogenic differentiation of hMSCs. hMSCs were seeded onto the Col membranes, which were then integrated in between the layered PCL constructs. The assessment of the osteogenic *in vitro* experiments by examining key

osteogenic markers and proliferation indicates a commitment of hMSCs to the osteogenic differentiation lineage. The CLIP-Col construct remained stable and structurally intact after 28 d of *in vitro* culture. Easy handling, retained structural stability, thin

shape and osteoconductivity makes this Col membrane an excellent candidate for delivering osteogenically primed cells into the layered construct, opening avenues for potential *in vivo* investigation. The Bio-Gide® Col membrane consisting of Col type I and III

is derived from porcine skin and non-crosslinked, however, Bio-Gide[®] also has a variant of the Col membrane that is crosslinked with 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-carbodiimide (EDC)/N-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) and was shown to be less prone to shrinking and possibly degradation. However, the crosslinked variant showed increased matrix rigidity and impeded cell migration [15].

The concept of employing a layered configuration to facilitate the spatial distribution of biologic substances within the construct has been demonstrated in previous research. A layered construct composed of alternating electro-spun polylactic acid (PLLA)/gelatin nanofibers and hMSCs meshes has been created with the aim to enhance bone repair [23]. Additionally, recent research shows the development of PCL or titanium constructs employing the LEGO[®]-inspired brick arrangements to be used to repair or augment bony defects [24, 25]. The assembly of these constructs are based on small blocks, while the here proposed approach revolves around a user-friendly layer-by-layer system that could be applied intraoperatively. This system allows for the development of a variety of customizable multicomponent constructs (figure 1). Through this layer-based approach different materials can be easily combined as demonstrated by creating a layered osteochondral construct [26]. By modulating the porosity of each layer, an outer frame with lower porosity to mimic cortical bone and an inner bulk with higher porosity emulating trabecular bone can be created. Furthermore, this approach allows for spatial delivery options of biological elements including different cell types with potential co-culture systems, bioactive factors, or membranes to create a multicomponent construct. The layer-based approach accommodates the real-time intraoperative integration of autologous substances such as stromal vascular fraction or bone marrow aspirate concentrate into the bone graft substitute prior to implantation. The addition of the Col membrane offers an additional advantage, namely the seeded cells are retained within the layer where they were seeded, rather than falling through the large macropores to the lower layer as seen in pilot studies (figure S1). Although, the large macropores of the LEGO[®]-inspired construct would cause the cells to fall through the scaffold, this aspect could aid in prevention of necrotic core formation, since it would allow for cell and nutrient diffusion and potentially vessel infiltration.

To demonstrate the osteogenic capabilities of this layered system, a Col membrane was selected due to its efficacy in promoting osteogenesis through various applications including hydrogels, membranes, or sponges [27]. Extensive research has been focused on Col sponges which have been clinically used in conjunction with BMP-2 for repairing bony defects [28]. Also, Col membranes have been utilized in clinical settings to support bone guided regeneration in

medicine and dentistry [29]. Within the scope of this study, the Col membranes allowed for hMSCs to differentiate into osteoblastic lineage upon osteogenic medium treatment, while being incorporated in the layered PCL constructs. Other Col-based membranes including Lyostypt[®] (Braun) and Col cell carrier[®] (Viscofan Bioengineering) were also tested. However, due to limitations such as swelling and structural breaking, respectively (data not shown), these Col membranes were excluded from this study.

An increased activity and staining of ALP, the main osteogenic marker on the protein level, of the cells was under osteogenic condition compared to basal medium was shown. Moreover, expression levels of important transcription factors for hMSCs differentiation (RUNX2, SOX9, SP7) and genes responsible for matrix production and regulation (COL1A1, ALPL, IBSP and SPP1) were increased in response to osteogenic conditions. Although, results were mostly statistically non-significant, observed trends were consistent for different analysis, thus potentially showing biological relevance. High standard deviations are commonly observed when using hMSCs due to donor variability, which was also something that could also be observed for hMSCs on CCP stained with Alizarin Red for mineralization (figure S2(a)).

One of the main indicators of osteogenic differentiation is the assessment of mineral deposition. This assessment is commonly conducted through staining techniques such as Alizarin Red or OsteoImage[®] to visualize mineralization. However, a significant challenge arises because Col membranes, like many biomaterials, stain highly false positive when using these methods. Consequently, due to the extremely high staining of uncultured Col membranes (figure S2(b)), distinguishing mineralization either deposited by differentiated hMSCs, which could be observed on CCP (figure S2(a)), or artifacts from non-specific deposition on the biomaterial during culture presents a difficulty. The absence of conclusive mineral deposition results stands as a limitation of this study.

PCL was selected as the foundational material for each layer due to its favorable properties including ease of 3D printability, biodegradability, and robust mechanical strength. Given the load-bearing nature of a large segmental mandibular defect the structural integrity of the implanted scaffold becomes important to withstand the fixation of a screw-plate system. However, the layered construct might exhibit reduced mechanical properties compared to a bulk scaffold, nevertheless the layered construct should possess sufficient mechanical strength to withstand forces associated with screw fixation, and clinically, load would be distributed over an implanted metal plate that fixates the bone. The scaffold is initially expected to provide mechanical reinforcement until the formation of new tissue replaces the scaffold. Therefore, it is important that the PCL scaffold degrades completely.

Degradation rate of PCL has already been widely studied and shown that molecular weight and porosity can highly influence the degradation rate [30, 31]. It is therefore expected that the here presented LEGO[®]-inspired construct would degrade faster than a bulk scaffold, due to its macroscopic pores giving higher surface area of PCL exposed. However, exact degradation rates should be tested during *in vivo* studies and could potentially be controlled by different molecular weights to tweak the desired biosorption rate.

A major drawback of the *in vivo* implantation of traditional 3D printed scaffolds in bulk form is the potential formation of a necrotic core due to limited oxygen diffusion and nutrient supply. To prevent this, the layered construct presents the possibility to create a pre-acellularized/pre-vascularized system containing endothelial cells within its layers, capable of anastomosing with native vessels post implantation, a future perspective of this study [32]. Furthermore, to enhance successful bone repair, the incorporation of innervation alongside vascularization can be applied to the system. The combined elements would increase the functional approach to create a bone graft substitute. Ultimately, to fully evaluate the osteogenic potential of the layered construct, the final assessments involve an *in vivo* animal study. Such an investigation would serve as a pivotal step before clinical translation can be considered and remains a limitation of this study.

5. Conclusions

In this study, the development of a patient-specific 3D printed LEGO[®]-inspired layered construct composed of PCL with hMSCs seeded on Col membrane embedded within layers was successfully established. Herein, the *in vitro* osteogenic potential of a layer-based multicomponent construct was demonstrated. The adaptability of this system allows for the generation of customizable multicompetent constructs and facilitates the distribution of biological elements within the construct. The versatility of the fabrication system has the potential to bridge the gap in creating a functional bone graft substitute, within the operating theatre, that is tailored for the task of repairing large mandibular defects.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

Acknowledgments

Schematic figures were created with BioRender.com. LEGO[®] is a trademark of the LEGO Group of

companies which does not sponsor, authorize or endorse this article.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest with the presented work.

Ethics statement

The Swiss Human Research Act does not apply to research which involves anonymized biological material and/or anonymously collected or anonymized health-related data. Therefore, this project does not need to be approved by the ethics committee. General Consent which also covers anonymization of health-related data and biological material was obtained.

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